

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF SOME 2-SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES OF TRICYCLO [5.2.1.0^{2,6}]DECAN

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Abstract

Based on individual exo- and endo-isomers of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-carboxylic acid, various nitrogen-containing derivatives were synthesized: amides, thioamides, amines, alkylamines, amidines. Antiviral properties tested.

Keywords: tetrahydrodicyclopentadiene, exo- and endo-isomers of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-carboxylic acid, antiviral activity.

Introductions.

The insecticidal activity of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane derivatives is widely known [1]. However, their antiviral activity has not yet been studied. This prompted us to obtain and test in this regard some of its nitrogen-containing derivatives. Direct functionalization of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (tetrahydrodicyclopentadiene) would be a convenient method for the preparation of such compounds.

Results and discussion.

Considering the foregoing, we developed a procedure for carboxylation (1) with formic acid in oleum, which led to the formation of a mixture of exo- and endo-isomers of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-carboxylic acid (2) and (3), respectively [2]. It has been established by GLC that the percentage of isomeric acids varies

greatly (from 30% to 70% for each isomer) depending on the temperature and reaction time.

Amides of isomeric carboxylic acids (4) and (5) were obtained by converting a mixture of acids (2) and (3) into a mixture of the corresponding acid chlorides, followed by treatment with ammonia. Exo-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-endo-2-carboxamide (4) was isolated by crystallization and saponified to acid (2). The mixture of amides remaining in the mother liquor, enriched in the endo-isomer, was also subjected to saponification. From the resulting mixture of acids, endo-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-exo-2-carboxylic acid (3) was isolated by crystallization and converted into the corresponding amide (5). The structure of carboxylic acids (2) and (3) was confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis.

From a mixture of acids (2) and (3) without separation of exo- and endo-isomers, the ratio of which after synthesis was 25% and 73%, respectively, a number of N-substituted derivatives were synthesized: tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-methyl)carboxamide (6), tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-dimethyl)carboxamide (7), tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-ureido)carboxamide (8), tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-thioureido)carboxamide (9).

The action of a mixture of amides (4) and (5), in the presence of sodium methoxide, with bromine syn-

thesized urethane (10), which was hydrolyzed with water without isolation to 2-amino-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (11) [3].

From the same mixture of amides, nitrile (12) was obtained by boiling for many hours in thionyl chloride, which was then reduced to 2-aminomethyltricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (13) with lithium aluminum hydride. Amidoxime (14) was obtained from nitrile (12) by reaction with a large excess of hydroxylamine in an alkaline medium.

The antiviral activity of the synthesized compounds was studied according to the method described in [4]. As can be seen from Table 1, only two compounds (6) and (9) exhibit moderate activity with low

toxicity. Most of the other compounds have areas of cytotoxic action that do not allow one to notice the antiviral effect, if any.

Table 1.

Results of testing the synthesized compounds for antiviral activity.

# Sabs.	Yield, %	Melting point, °C	Testing facts	
			The size of the zone of cytotoxicity, mm	The size of the plaque suppression zone, mm
4	21	127-129	6	0
5	57	159-160	16	0
6	66	105-107	0	15
7	21	81-83	26	0
8	28	187-190	0	0
9	22	197-199	0	18
11	17	>290 dest.	30	0
13	80	>300 dest.	50	0
14	35	185-187	10	0

Materials and methods.

IR spectra were recorded on a UR-10 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets in the range 450-3700 cm^{-1} . GLC analysis was performed on a Tsvet-102 chromatograph, glass column 1 m, diameter 3 mm, inerton AW HMDS with 5% apieson L, carrier gas helium, 40 ml/min.

Exo-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-endo-2-carboxylic acid (2). A mixture of 40 ml of formic acid, 21 g of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (1) and 200 ml of dichloroethane is added dropwise to 420 ml of 20% oleum, cooled to 13 °C with stirring, over an hour at such a rate that the temperature does not rise above 16 °C. The mixture is poured onto the lud. The dichloroethane layer is separated and extracted with 250 ml of 10% potassium hydroxide solution. The alkaline extract is acidified. The precipitated precipitate is filtered off, washed with water and dried in air. Yield 14.2.g (50%). GC: (2), 27%, 116 s; (3), 73%, 149 s.

Exo-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-endo-2-carboxamide (4). To 13 g of a mixture of acids (2) and (3) obtained by the previous method, add 10 ml of thionyl chloride and heat on a water bath for 1 hour. Excess thionyl chloride is distilled off in vacuo with dry benzene. A solution of acid chloride in dry tetrahydrofuran is added dropwise with ice-cooling and stirring to 60 ml of 25% ammonia solution. The precipitate formed is filtered off, washed and dried in air. To the product is added 20 ml of hexane, brought to a boil and the hot hexane solution is decanted. The operation is repeated 2 more times. Amide crystals (4) precipitated from hexane are dried in air. Yield 2.7 g (21%). M.p. 127-129 oC.

Endo-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-exo-2-carboxamide (5). The mother liquor obtained by isolating the amide (4) is evaporated. To 10 g of a mixture of amides add 100 ml of 74% sulfuric acid and heat to 80 °C with stirring. Within 50 min. sprinkle with portions of 30 g of sodium nitrite. Stir for another 10 minutes. The reaction mass is diluted with water. The precipitate that forms is filtered off, washed and air dried. Yield 7 g (70%). The resulting mixture of acids (2) and (3) is subjected to repeated recrystallization from ethyl acetate, monitoring the purity of the precipitated acid by GLC for the residual content of acid (2). As a result of 24-fold recrystallization, 1.5 g of acid (3) with 98% content of the main substance was isolated. Amide (5) was obtained from

0.5 g of acid (3) according to the method described above. Yield 90%. M.p. 159-160 °C.

Tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-methyl)carboxamide (6). Obtained by a method similar to obtaining amide (4). Yield 66%. M. p. 105-107 °C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1650, 3470.

Tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-dimethyl)carboxamide (7). Obtained according to the method for amide (4). Yield 21%. M. p. 81-83 °C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1650, 3470.

Tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-ureido)carboxamide (8). Obtained according to the method for amide (4). Yield 28%. M. p. 189-190 °C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1670, 1510, 3430.

Tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-thioureido)carboxamide (9). Obtained according to method)4). Yield 22%. M. p. 197-199°C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1680, 1620, 1250, 3190.

2-Aminomethyltricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (13). To 15 g of amides (3) and (4) add 20 ml of thionyl chloride and boil for 30 hours. Excess thionyl chloride is distilled off with dry benzene. The residue is dissolved in 30 ml of dry ether and poured over 30 minutes into an ice-cooled suspension of lithium aluminum hydride (10 g) in 200 ml of dry ether. Stir for another 10 minutes. Lithium aluminum hydride is neutralized with water and then with alkali. The ethereal solution is separated and passed through hydrogen chloride. The precipitated amine hydrochloride is filtered off. Yield 15 g (80%). Decomposes without melting above 300 °C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1580, 3150.

2-Amidoxime-tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]decane (14). To 2 g of nitrile (12), obtained according to the previous method, add 12 g of hydroxylamine sulfate, 10.4 g of potassium carbonate in 80 ml of water. Boil 24 hours. Pour into water, filter. The filtrate is extracted with ether. After drying, the solvent is evaporated. Dry benzene is added to the residue and hydrogen chloride is passed through until the resulting precipitate dissolves. Benzene is evaporated. Yield 1 g (35%). M. p. 185-187 °C. IR spectrum, cm^{-1} : 1600, 1640, 3160, 3440.

Conclusions.

By recrystallization of amides of tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-carboxylic acid, it was possible to obtain its individual exo- and endo-isomers. Amines and amidoximes were synthesized on their basis. It was

found that only tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-methyl)carboxamide and tricyclo[5.2.1.0^{2,6}]deca-2-(N-thioureido)carboxamide have moderate antiviral activity with zero toxicity.

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